

Reaction of Tungsten Pentabromide with Nitroanilines, Aminophenols, Aminobenzoic Acids, Anilides, and 2-Aminopyridine

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Formation of several complex compounds of WBr_5 with nitroanilines, aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, anilides, and 2-aminopyridine has been studied.

The tendency of tungsten to form complexes varies from one valency state to another. Several compounds of WCl_6 and $WOCl_4$ with nitroanilines, aminophenols, anilides, and amides have been prepared by Prasad and Krishnaiah¹⁻². The work has further been extended to study the formation of compounds of WBr_5 with similar organic substances.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either of E. Merck or B. D. H. extra-pure quality. Ether used was dried over sodium metal and finally distilled over sodium hydride.

Tungsten pentabromide³ was prepared by passing bromine vapour over red-hot tungsten metal, placed in a silica tube; excess of bromine was expelled by a stream of nitrogen. The product was collected in ether and analysed for purity.

All the reactions were carried out in glass-stoppered vessels under anhydrous condition. An ethereal solution of tungsten pentabromide was added to the solution of the organic substances in ether when the complex compounds separated immediately. The precipitate was allowed to settle and filtered through a dry filter paper. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with dry ether till free of the reactants, filter-pressed, and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

In the case of 2-aminopyridine, a dilute solution of the base in ether was added to the WBr_5 solution till nearly complete precipitation, keeping WBr_5 solution in slight excess. The precipitate was then washed, dried in vacuum, and analysed.

Tungsten was estimated as WO_3 , bromine by Piria and Schiff's method as $AgBr$, and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by microanalytical methods in a few cases.

1. Prasad and Krishnaiah, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 177.
2. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 757.
3. Gerstl, *Ber.*, 1875, **5**, 121.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Colour.	%Tungsten.		%Bromine.		%Nitrogen.		%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
			Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	Dark yellow	14.92	14.44	32.57	31.39	10.87	10.98	28.29	28.25	2.33	2.35
2.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	Yellow	14.81	14.44	32.28	31.39	..	..	..	..	..	..
3.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	White	15.10	14.44	32.41	31.39	..	..	..	..	..	..
4.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	Brown	16.93	16.29	36.29	35.42	..	..	31.81	31.86	3.14	3.10
5.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	Blue	16.27	16.29	36.79	35.42	6.42	6.20	..	..	..	..
6.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenol	Grey	17.10	16.29	36.82	35.42	..	..	..	..	..	..
7.	<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Ash	13.99	14.38	32.90	31.27	..	..	..	..	..	..
8.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Cream	13.79	14.38	31.98	31.27	5.51	5.47	32.79	32.83	2.77	2.73
9.	<i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Dirty white	13.50	14.36	32.52	31.27	..	..	..	..	..	..
10.	Acetanilide	Cream	14.34	14.01	33.22	31.77	5.49	5.56	..	..	..	..
11.	<i>p</i> -Aminoacetanilide	Cream	13.25	13.79	30.71	29.98	10.52	10.49	35.89	35.98	3.71	3.74
12.	2-Aminopyridine	Olive-green	17.20	17.45	36.95	37.95	13.41	13.28	..	..	..	..

Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, except those with *m*-nitroaniline and *m*-aminobenzoic acid which are white. These are almost insoluble in all the usual organic solvents, except *o*-aminophenol which is slightly soluble in dioxane. The compounds are stable in dry atmosphere; but on exposure to moisture these start decomposing, but not so readily as observed in the case of secondary and tertiary amine complexes⁵. Their stability is of the order of primary amine complexes due to strong $-\text{NH}_2$ group present in the molecule. Aqueous extract of the complexes responds to the test of bromine, probably due to decomposition of the compound or to the hydrolysis of WBr_5 . The compounds do not sharply melt and decompose over 150° . Colour and analytical data of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

DISCUSSION

From the results, it is evident that five molecules of nitroanilines, aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, anilides, or 2-aminopyridine combine with one molecule of tungsten pentabromide in the cold to yield the complex compounds which are similar to those obtained with aromatic amines and bases⁴⁻⁵. The hydroxyl, carboxyl, nitro, and $-\text{NH}$ groups do not co-ordinate in presence of a strong donor group like $-\text{NH}_2$. A similar result was obtained in the case of *p*-aminodiethylaniline with WCl_6 by Prasad and Krishnaiah⁶.

As the compounds are insoluble in all common organic solvents, it has not been possible to determine their molecular weights by cryoscopic method.

In the earlier communications^{4,5,6}, two probable structures of the compounds with aromatic amines have been discussed and similar structures are possible in these compounds too. Moreover, the magnetic susceptibilities of *m*-nitroaniline and *p*-aminobenzoic acid show them to be paramagnetic in nature and both the structures are in agreement with this observation. Thus with the co-ordination number six, these may form a 6-co-ordinated complex of d^4sp type, keeping four bromine atoms out in the ionic form; with co-ordination number 8, two bromine atoms are in ionic form, forming a dipositive complex tungsten ion of d^4sp^3 type. This latter structure seems to be more probable as co-ordination number 8 with tungsten is quite common, e.g. $\text{W}(\text{CN})_8^{4-}$ ⁷ and this may be represented as

(X = $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{COOH}$ or $-\text{NO}_2$ group; R = C_6H_4)

and the similar structure can also be formulated for anilides and 2-aminopyridine.

4. Prasad and Swarup, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1965, 339, 220.

5. Prasad and Swarup, *Compt. rend.*, 1964, 259, 3575.

6. Prasad and Krishnaiah, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 182.

7. Cartmell and Fowles, "Valency and Molecular Structure", Butterworth Scientific Publication, London, 1956, p. 208.

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